

Supplementary Material

Appendix 2. Simulated scenario

OhioHealth Learning Scenario Development Form

Scenario Title: Post thyroidectomy hematoma

Target Learners: Physicians Nurses EMS Others: Surgery Residents

Estimated Simulation Time: 10 min **Estimated Debriefing Time:** 30 **Estimated Total Time:** 40

Curricular Information

Primary Learning Objectives:

At the end of this simulation experience learners will be able to:

1. demonstrate the ability to identify post thyroidectomy hematoma
2. demonstrate clinical skills for managing post thyroidectomy hematoma
3. demonstrate teamwork and communication skills among team
4. demonstrate leadership/decision making skills

Critical Actions Checklist:

Complete

Critical Action

- | | |
|--------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 1. Performing a focused examination of the neck |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 2. Communicating to the team about the findings and management plan |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 3. Leading the team to execute the management plan |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 4. Informing the attending surgeon of situation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 5. Planning definitive hemostasis in OR |

Case Narrative

Name: David Brown **DOB:** 01/01/1950 **Age:** 69 **Sex:** M **Weight:** 105
Kg Height: 1.80m

Chief Complaint: Neck swelling, stridor

History of Present Illness/ Injury:

David initially presented with a thyroid goiter which was growing progressively for the last 2 years.

After management for hypothyroidism, he is now euthyroid and was planned for thyroidectomy.

He has controlled hypertension 5 years and has no allergy or any other relevant past medical history.

Past Medical: Controlled Hypertension since 5 years	Surgical History: Knee arthroscopy under spinal anesthesia 3 years ago
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Medications: Losartan 50 mg OD	Allergies: None
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Social History: ETOH: Occasionally Tobacco: No Illicit: No	Family History: Mother: Not contributory Father: Not contributory
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Physical Exam

GCS: *Eyes:4 Verbal:5 Motor:6 Total: 15*

General: Lying in bed with mild respiratory distress

HEENT: Mild stridor, neck swelling

Cardiovascular: BP: 130/80 mmHg HR: 115 b/min

Pulmonary: RR: 12 Sat: 98% on 100% O₂

Abdomen: soft on palpation, no organomegaly

Extremities: normal

Skin: normal

Neuro: normal

GU: normal

Other:

ROS: No laryngospasm, bronchospasm, residual anesthesia

Discussion

Overview of roles

Lead participant	Surgery resident
Present at start	(SimMan®): Mr David PACU Nurse (co-facilitator)
Additional	Anaesthesiologist Surgeon

Prepare the scenario

Isolate the lead participant outside the simulation room/pre-brief

Prepare the other participants in the simulation room:

- Allocate roles and briefing cards (scripts)
- Arrange participants in the scenario according to their roles
- Have the Surgical resident 'outside' the simulation room

Briefing in the simulation room

This is PACU.

The patient is David, who is admitted 2 hours ago following thyroidectomy. He has been getting progressive neck swelling and increasing respiratory rate.

David is being cared for by a nurse who is worried about him.

Briefing for the lead participant

You are a Surgery Resident

You are the resident on call.

You are called by the PACU nurse for help.

How to start the scenario

Cue lead participant to enter the PACU

COPY OF BRIEFING CARDS (Scripts)

– PACU Nurse (co-facilitator)

You are a PACU nurse who has been looking after David. You are concerned that he is becoming more short of breath. He is feeling dizzy.

Handover with SBAR:

S situation:

- I am so glad that you came right away !!!
- This is David, a 69-year-old male. His neck is becoming more swollen in the last 1 hour

B background:

- David is 2 hours post admission. David initially presented with a thyroid goiter. A total thyroidectomy was performed without any intra-operative complications, and David was admitted to the PACU with expected discharge to the floor in the next 3 hours.

A assessment:

- A: Patent
- B: RR: 12 Sat: 98% on 100% O₂
- C: BP: 130/80 mmHg HR: 115 b/min
- D: Alert
- E: Swelling noted at the surgical site. There is an obvious thyroidectomy incision and increased swelling of the neck. The surgical area feels tense.

R recommendation:

- Can you please check David? I am worried about him.

Prompts:

1. If tapped once on the shoulder – say, “Do you agree with me that he is getting in trouble?”
2. If tapped two times on the shoulder – tell the resident, “I have been really worried about his increasing neck swelling “
3. If tapped three times on the shoulder – tell the resident, “He is so sick, you have to get someone here to help.”

– Anaesthesiologist

You may be called to help manage a case in PACU. Wait to be told to enter by the facilitator

– Surgeon

You may be called to help manage a case in PACU. Give advice on phone.

– OR Nurse

You may be called to book OR room. Answer on phone that all OR rooms are occupied.

Consult(s)/ Clinical Progression

David Brown is a 69-year-old gentleman who underwent a total thyroidectomy 2 hours ago and has now been transferred to the PACU. His nurse states that he is deteriorating. On further questioning, the nurse states that his neck appears more swollen compared to an hour ago. David is initially speaking but becomes more obtunded as the scenario progresses. His oxygen saturation continues to decrease until the hematoma is evacuated at the bedside and definitive plans made to return to the operating room.

The goals of the scenario for learners is to use effective communication and teamwork to manage an expanding post-thyroidectomy hematoma in an unstable patient. Learners should demonstrate decision making and leadership skills to perform bedside hematoma decompression in a clinically deteriorating patient and to make arrangements for definitive hemostasis.

Instructor Notes

Scenario Branch Points, Modifiers and Triggers

Patient State	Patient Status	Learner Actions, Modifiers & Triggers to Next State	
<p>2.</p> <p>Rhythm: ---</p> <p>HR:</p> <p>BP:</p> <p>RR:</p> <p>O₂Sat:</p> <p>CO₂:</p> <p>Temp:</p> <p>Eyes: ---</p> <p>Lung Sounds:</p> <p>R: ---</p> <p>L: ---</p> <p>Heart Sounds:</p> <p>---</p> <p>Bowel Sounds:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If further delay, patient becomes unresponsive to questions except for moaning. - BP 166/84; HR 140; O₂ sat 86%; shallow breaths, RR 25; airway edematous and difficult to intubate. 	<p align="center"><u>Learner Actions</u></p> <p><u>Step 2: Management of crisis</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - remove dressing and Steristrips - release skin sutures - release deep sutures - evacuate hematoma - place temporary packing - consider intubation - informed OR of take back - exchange information with the team when the patient's oxygen saturation dropped - work effectively with the team when the patient's oxygen saturation dropped - listened attentively to the stated needs of information provided by the team during the crisis - informed the Attending Surgeon of situation - demonstrate respect and sensitivity to anesthesia regarding desaturation during difficult airway management (if applicable) 	<p align="center"><u>Modifiers</u></p> <p>History of thyroidectomy several hours ago should increase suspicion for hematoma collection.</p> <p>Delay in identification of hematoma leads to continually decreasing O₂ saturation of 1% for every minute of delay</p> <hr/> <p align="center"><u>Triggers</u></p> <p><u>Prompts:</u></p> <p>Two taps co-facilitator – “I have been really worried about his increasing neck swelling”</p>

Scenario Branch Points, Modifiers and Triggers

Patient State	Patient Status	Learner Actions, Modifiers & Triggers to Next State	
<p>3.</p> <p>Rhythm: ---</p> <p>HR:</p> <p>BP:</p> <p>RR:</p> <p>O₂Sat:</p> <p>CO₂:</p> <p>Temp:</p> <p>Eyes: ---</p> <p>Lung Sounds:</p> <p>R: ---</p> <p>L: ---</p> <p>Heart Sounds:</p> <p>---</p> <p>Bowel Sounds:</p>	<p>Following the hematoma release, patient shows improvement in respiratory status and is responsive with O₂ saturation improved to 98%.</p> <p>BP 130/83, HR 100, RR 14.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Learner Actions</u></p> <p>Step 3: Plan safe transfer of the patient to OR for definitive hemostasis</p>	<p align="center"><u>Modifiers</u></p> <p>Scenario ends when the team informed the surgeon and decides to transfer safely David to OR for definitive hemostasis</p>
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognized that the crisis has been managed - verified availability of OR - verified that the team is ready to transport the patient to OR for definitive management 	<p align="center"><u>Triggers</u></p> <p><u>Prompt:</u></p> <p>Three taps to co-facilitator – “He is so sick, you have to get someone here to help.”</p> <p>One Tap to OR nurse – “all OR rooms are occupied”</p>

Moulage

Neck fresh collar
incision with dressing

Steristrips/oozing from
incision

Swollen visibly swollen due
to clotted blood deep to strep
muscles

Environment

Patient Props:

Type	Manikin, wearing a patient gown
Details	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- SimMan® (Mr David) is lying in the bed- A large clotted hematoma is deep to the strap muscles and skin placed over the mannequin's neck.- There is a thyroidectomy incision closed with interrupted subcutaneous sutures with obvious swelling.- SimMan®'s airway is set to be edematous and difficult, though not impossible, to intubate.
Position	Lying in bed supine
Equipment on	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- NIBP- ECG- Pulse oximeter- G18 IV in place- On 100% O₂ by Mask

Room Props:

Monitors

- NIBP
- ECG
- Pulse oximeter

Equipment

- Scissors
- Scalpel
- Sutures
- Sponges
- Betadine solution
- Surgical gloves/Masks/Gowns
- Resuscitation drugs cart (drugs are not to be drawn)
- Suction
- O₂ tank with Laerdal bag and mask
- Oral pharyngeal airways (OPA)
- Nasal pharyngeal airways (NPA)
- Laryngoscope with Mac 3 and 4 blades available
- Selection of endotracheal tubes

- Stylet
- Bougie
- LMA size 3, 4 and 5
- Stethoscope
- Extra Anesthesia drugs:
- IV equipment: **IV pressure bags**
- IV fluids

Simulation Room Type: PACU

Distractors:

None

Staffing/ Confederates:

- PACU Nurse (co-facilitator)
- Anesthesiologist (Available)
- Surgeon (Available by phone)